

A Study on emerging role of online payment platform in post covid era

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Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic has boosted the use of digital and contactless payments. These payments include transfers initiated via online banking, a mobile banking app or an automated transfer. This study tries to analyze the awareness among the users of online payment applications and to find out the most preferred online payment application among users. For this purpose I conducted own research with sample size 100. The research findings confirms that the online payment platform have more impact in post covid era. . Most of the users extremely aware about various online payments modes and its merits and demerits also. For statistical processing of results I used chi-square test and Weighted mean

Keywords: Online payment, Covid –19, Digital awareness

Introduction

During the pandemic, more consumers became comfortable purchasing routine items online or with their smart phones to avoid risky in-person interactions. Lockdowns and restrictions have resulted in changes in consumer behavior. One of the direct results of the pandemic was a noticeable growth in online shopping. The e-commerce market is more popular than ever before, thanks to the adoption of ordering groceries and other everyday goods online. Throughout history, individuals have used different payment systems for purchasing products and services. The money-transferring apps can come in handy when you need to transfer or pay money instantly, online bill payment and mobile recharge within a few minutes. By using money transfer apps, you can securely and digitally transfer money to anyone you want, both domestically and internationally. One of the main benefits of money transferring apps is convenience because it gives customers the benefit of emitting whenever they need to, wherever they are. Several money transferring apps allow the users to make online payment, fund transfer and operate their cash anywhere anytime. COVID-19 is further increasing the need for E-cash transactions. It creates greater demand to money transferring apps where cashless transactions are prioritized. The covid-19 pandemic could move the world more rapidly towards digital payments. Payment systems have demonstrated that they are dependable and durable, and continue to command a high level of confidence from the general population. However, closure of businesses and the lockdown have resulted in lower transaction volumes overall. To aid the recovery and lead the emergence into this new normal, it is imperative for the digital payments ecosystem to evolve rapidly and help

shape the post-COVID era. The growth of the internet, mobiles and communication technology added a different dimension to money transferring.

Objectives of the study

Online payment platform are to reduce the costs and risks of handling cash, increase the ease of conducting online transactions, and increase transparency among monetary transactions among people. The main objectives of this study are:

1. To analyze the awareness among the users of online payment applications
2. To find out the most preferred online payment application among users

Statement of the problem

COVID-19 made vibrations in the operations as well as product and services of banks .It create greater demand to money transferring apps where cashless transactions are prioritized. Mobile users can now a day use the smart phones to make money transaction or payment by using applications installed in the phone. When temporary problem occurs while using online payment platform, it creates in-convenience to customers. In a paperless transaction; many problems of security are involved. The people are afraid about the secrecy of the transactions. Therefore, this study aims to analysis and find out awareness and preference towards online payment platform after the occurrence of COVID-19

Scope of the study

Saving time and saving money is a basic human wish and need. Prior to the COVID-19 outbreaks, digital payments, especially mobile payments, were growing incrementally. Due to the drastic changes I have to decide to do study on the impact of COVID-19 on the use of online payment platform among people. Different classes of people's are transacting through different payment apps. The study further helps to improve the

awareness among the users of different online payment applications.

Limitations of the study

The study is done with reference to Trissur city so it difficult to study the impact of COVID -19 of large population

The sample size is limited to 100 respondents.

Review of Literature

1. A general scanning of the literature available in India from different published sources indicates that very few detailed studies have been conducted in India in the field of emerging role of online payment platform in post covid era.
2. Singhal Rashi (2021): quoted in her paper "Impact and Importance of Digital Payment in India" that services offered by banks in digital form provides various opportunities to the banks when it comes to the benefit of their customers. The shoppers have a great impression along with a worthwhile effect upon the use of digital payments services. As one of the largest providers of financial and monetary services in our smart cities and the bush of rural areas, business banks provide inimitable services to their potential customers. She has founded that RBI and Indian government has brought up some noticeable acceptances with an entry of a mode such as non-financial system of deferred payments
3. M.Thangajesu Sathish, R.Sermakani, and G.Sudha (2020) this study is revealed that the traditional system of cash transaction cannot completely be replaced by card or e-payment system. People can adopt and use their mobile wallets for the payment transaction, fund transfer, purchasing groceries and paying bills etc. The study has discussed the trust is the main factor affecting users' satisfaction directly and it impacts on many users intention to adopt mobile wallets
4. G.Sudha and M.Thangajesu Sathish (2020) article is revealed that after demonetization retailers will adopt the digital payment methods. The researcher analysed to find out the payment methods between the pre and post period of demonetization. Most of the retailers used their payments through using various applications.

5. G.Sudha and Dr.V.Sornaganesh (2019) article is revealed that after demonetization changes in buying behaviour are clearly explained. After demonetization the main impact is reduce the paper money and increase the digital cash. Most of the customers used digital cash after the demonetization, used through the mobile applications, Internet Banking, etc., for paying their bills

Research Methodology

Research Design

The study follows the descriptive method of research to measure, evaluate and analyze the impact of online payment apps among customers. Primary data has been collected through questionnaire

Research Approach

The approach adopted in this study is survey approach.

Tools used for the study

Statistical tools are involved in carrying out a study include planning, designing, collecting data, analyzing, drawing meaningful interpretation and reporting of the research findings. The tools are Chi-Square test and weighted mean

Data Source

Both primary and secondary data used for the study. The Primary data for this study was collected through questionnaire and responses collected through Google form. Secondary data was collected from external sources like Websites, Journals in form of review of Literature with references.

Sampling Area

Trissur district is selected for taking the samples for the study.

Sample Size

The sample size of the study is limited to 100.

Sampling Procedure

The sampling procedure used in the study is Convenience sampling. A convenience sample is a type sampling method where the sample is taken from a group of People easy to contact or to reach

Analysis and Interpretation

The data collected for the study showed in this chapter. The results are show in the form of test and ranking method are conducted and necessary explanations are given below

Table 4.1 Relationship between gender and awareness towards online payment applications

Gender	Known about online payment applications		Total
	Yes	No	
Male	30	18	48
Female	32	20	52
Total	62	38	100

Source; primary data

Null hypothesis (h0): There is no significant association between gender and Awareness towards online platform applications Alternative

hypothesis (h1): There is association between gender and Awareness towards online platform applications

**Table 4.2 table of calculation
CHI SQUARE TEST**

Observed frequencies	Expected frequencies	(O -E)2	(O-E)2 /E
30	29.76	0.0576	0.00193
18	18.24	0.0576	0.00315
32	32.24	0.0576	0.00178
20	19.76	0.0576	0.00291
		0.0576	0.00977

Table value at 5% level of significance and 1 degree of freedom=3.841 Decision: since the calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value χ^2_{table} is accepted.

Interpretation: There is no significant association between the gender and awareness towards online payment platform

Table 4.3 Table Showing Respondents Preference towards Money Transferring app

Factors	Rank Values	5	4	3	2	1	15	Weighted Mean
Google Pay		59 (295)	15 (60)	19 (57)	1 (2)	6 (6)	420	28
Phone Pay		11 (55)	55 (220)	23 (69)	9 (18)	2 (2)	364	24.27
Paytm		23 (115)	21 (84)	51 (153)	4 (8)	1 (1)	361	24.07
PayPal		2 (10)	6 (24)	5 (15)	46 (92)	41 (41)	182	12.13
Amazon pay		7 (35)	3 (12)	2 (6)	38 (76)	50 (50)	179	11.93
Total		510	400	300	196	100	1506	100

Sources: Primary Data

Criteria	Rank
Google Pay	1
Phone Pay	2
Paytm	3
PayPal	4
Amazon pay	5

Interpretation: It can be noted from the table No.4.3 that the respondents preference towards money transferring apps. Most preferable app by the respondents is Google Pay with mean value 28 and Amazon pay is least preferable app by the respondents, with mean value 11.93.

Findings

There is no significant association between the gender and awareness towards money transferring apps. Majority of the respondents prefer Google Pay for money transferring

The research reveals that majority of respondents like to continue use of the application after COVID effect

Suggestions

In order to attract more people to use this applications provide more rewards and offers Through giving more awareness about this application people are ready to use this one.

Conclusion.

Online payment platform bring tremendous changes in the economy. It plays an important part in our day to day life. Most of the respondents are aware about the services of money transferring apps. The digital payment had given relief and force to learn digital transaction after COVID effect. The study reveals that COVID-19 made most of the respondents switch to use money transferring apps instead of visiting bank branches for making transaction. The study shows that most preferable money transferring app by the users is Google Pay. Technology helps the customers to fulfill their needs from home itself. The money transferring apps made greater impact on their users after COVID-19 effect.

References

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